

A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: The article aims to study the current state of the occupational safety and health system in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its development paths. The importance of ensuring occupational safety and health, relevant legislation, existing problems in the system, and measures being taken to combat them will be analyzed. Strategies that should be implemented in this area in the future will also be considered.

Keywords: Occupational safety, labor protection, management system, legislation, production hazards, safe working conditions, occupational health.

Introduction: Occupational safety and health protection system is of great importance in the socio-economic development of every country. In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has paid great attention to strengthening labor safety legislation, reducing risks in production, and improving working conditions. No matter what environmental conditions a person operates in, there is a mutual interaction between the person and the environment. Therefore, human activity is directed towards two goals:

1. Achieving a specific effective goal and benefit during one's activities.
2. To eliminate unpleasant situations that arise during the period of activity, that is, to ensure that the activity is safe and harmless

Unfavorable situations are understood as harm to a person's life and health. Any situation, circumstance, or means that can harm a person's life and health during their activities are called hazards. Hazards can harm human health, endanger life, and disrupt the normal functioning of the body.

This article analyzes the changes in the labor protection and occupational safety management system of the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years and the ways for its future development.

Relevance of the topic: Occupational safety and health protection system is an integral part of economic and social development in the country. After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, many major steps were taken to update and modernize labor laws. Occupational safety issues ensure not only the efficiency of the production process, but also the protection of the health and life of citizens. Therefore, improving the system of occupational safety and health, increasing its effectiveness, and improving legislation in this area are extremely urgent issues today. [1]

Literature review: Scientific literature and research on occupational safety and health have been conducted in many areas. This includes an analysis of the experiences of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other countries. There are conclusions about major studies conducted in the field of occupational safety and modern management methods, as well as what approaches are needed to improve the effectiveness of the occupational safety system. Regulatory and legal documents developed by the Ministry of Poverty Reduction and Employment of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their application in practice. International experiences in creating a safe working environment and minimizing risks in production and methods of adapting them to the conditions of Uzbekistan. Research on the role of the management system in occupational safety and health and its effectiveness.[1,2,3]

Main part: Laws and regulations in the field of occupational safety and

health. The Republic of Uzbekistan has developed basic legislative and regulatory documents aimed at ensuring occupational safety. Among them are the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. OPF-410 dated September 22, 2016 "On Labor Protection", [1] the Labor Code adopted in 2022, and a number of other regulatory legal acts. These laws and regulations are aimed at improving working conditions and ensuring the safety and health of workers.

Occupational safety management system: The occupational safety management system in Uzbekistan includes several stages:

Occupational risk assessment, analysis of hazards and adverse events in production. Creating safe working conditions, Workers are provided with necessary protective equipment and technical safety equipment.

Education and training, Providing workers with safety training courses.

Monitoring and control. Supervision is carried out by organizations to ensure occupational safety. [4]

Problems and future development paths: Improving laws: Some laws and regulations in the field of occupational safety are outdated and need to be amended. Technological changes, the use of new technologies in production can lead to safety problems. Therefore, it is necessary to implement safety measures that are compatible with modern technologies.

Cultural approach, It is necessary to form a conscious approach to occupational safety issues among the population.[5]

Xulosa: The occupational safety management system in the Republic of Uzbekistan has reached important stages in its development. However, there are measures that need to be taken to further improve the system and ensure occupational safety. Laws and regulatory documents on occupational safety need to be constantly updated and adapted to new production conditions. In the future, updates, changes and new approaches in this area will help Uzbekistan further strengthen occupational safety on a global scale.

List of used literature.

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Labor Protection. September 22, 2016, No. ORQ-410.

URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/3031427>

2. Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. October 28, 2022, No. ORQ-798. URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/6257345>

3. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 1, 2019, No. 75. On approval of the Regulation on the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Industrial Safety.

URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/4169342>

4. REGULATION On the procedure for creating and organizing the activities of labor protection services in organizations. ANNEX 5 to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1066 dated December 31, 2018.

5. “REGULATION On the Procedure for Identification of Hazardous Production Facilities” issued as ANNEX 1 to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 271 dated December 10, 2008